

Effects of Stress, Anisotropy and Brittle-to-Ductile Transition on Fracturing and Fluid Flow in Shales

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Abstract

This paper aims at providing a better understanding of the fracturing behavior of shales due to shearing in relation to stress level, anisotropy and brittle-ductile transition, and the effects of fracturing to the changes in permeability and seismic velocities in shales. Triaxial compression tests were performed using a high-pressure and high-temperature (HPHT) triaxial cell on samples of Mancos shale cored horizontally parallel to the bedding plane. During triaxial shearing, the continuous changes in sample permeability, and the P and S wave velocities were simultaneously monitored during loading. The formation of fractures in the test samples during shearing was characterized. Structural anisotropy of shale is evaluated in terms of the shear wave splitting parameter. The results show complicated interactions between initial heterogeneity, brittle-to-ductile transition and stress level on the fracturing and the ensuing permeability changes during shearing of shales. An interesting observation was that tensile fracturing can occur in a compressional regime in shales due to shearing along pre-existing undulating bedding plane laminations. Notwithstanding these complex interactions, it was found that the shear wave splitting parameter can be a useful index for monitoring fracturing and permeability changes of shales during to shearing.

Introduction

Understanding the hydro-mechanical behavior of shale formations is becoming increasingly important as shales play important roles in the production of unconventional oil and gas resources as well as in geological carbon sequestration where shales typically form the cap rock above CO₂ storage reservoirs. Shales typically have very low permeability ranging from pico to micro Darcy orders (e.g., Brace, 1984; Neuzil, 1994) due to their very tight matrices that are mainly composed of kerogen, other organic matters, clay minerals and silica. Shale permeability is highly stress sensitive (Spencer 1989; Gutierrez et al. 2000). The wide-ranging variation of matrix permeability of shales can be attributed to their microstructure, which is often strongly anisotropic because of fissility and laminations along the bedding plane. The stress sensitivity of shale permeability becomes more pronounced when shale is fractured (Gutierrez et al., 2000).

Fracturing is often the only way to provide high permeability pathways for fluid flow and to extract fluid from or to inject fluids into shales. Fracturing and the resulting hydraulic properties of the fractured shale are strongly dependent on the tensile and shear strength properties but also on brittleness or ductility, which in turn depends on the stress level during fracturing, the diagenetic history of the shale and pore fluid composition. The mechanical response particularly failure and fracturing of shales are also strongly influenced by

microstructure. The stress sensitivity and anisotropy of fracturing behavior of shales is significant due to their laminated microstructure. However, the prominent layered microstructure of shale has not been fully considered even though it can result in strong hydro-mechanical anisotropy that can interact with the stress dependence and brittle-to-ductile transition in shale fracturing behavior.

The main goal of this paper is to improve the understanding of the hydro-mechanical characteristics of shale and their dependencies on stress level and microstructure. This improved understanding is crucial to reliably predicting the fracturing and fluid flow and leakage behavior of shale in many geoenvironmental applications. Three major topics are investigated in this paper. First is the effect of intrinsic structural anisotropy and stress anisotropies on fracturing behavior including induced fracture morphology. Second is the effect of fracturing on the changes in permeability during shearing. Third is the use of seismic wave velocities, particularly shear wave splitting, on characterizing the natural and fracturing-induced hydro-mechanical anisotropy of shales.

Test Sample and Triaxial Testing

Triaxial compression tests were carried out on Mancos shale plug samples, which were sheared at constant confining pressure conditions in a high pressure-high temperature (HPHT) triaxial cell equipped with 0.5 MHz-piezoelectric transducers. Two test samples were horizontally cored with 38 mm diameter from a block of Mancos shale retrieved from Douglas Creek Arch located between the Uinta and Piceance basins in Colorado, USA. Mancos shale is an organic rich shale of Cretaceous age and has a pronounced layered microstructure. The grain density is 2.68 g/cm^3 , and the porosity values of the tested samples were 5.8 and 6.6%. The samples were dried at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ prior to triaxial testing until the weight of the sample became constant. The horizontally-cored sample is enclosed in a rubber sleeve and placed in a triaxial cell that is capable of applying 69 MPa of cell pressure at a temperature of up to $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Both ends of core sample are confined with axial pistons through grooved metal plates to distribute compressed air. The cell pressures P_c of the two samples were maintained at 2 and 12 MPa using a precision ISCO 260D syringe pump. The axial load is generated by pushing an axial piston with another syringe pump (ISCO, 100DX) at a constant strain rate of $8.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ \%}/\text{min}$ near failure. The piston displacement is measured by using a LVDT whose accuracy is $\pm 0.25 \text{ \%}$ of 1 mm at full scale. The permeability changes of the test samples during shearing were characterized by injecting dry air from one end of core sample. Air permeability was converted to liquid permeability using the correction from Klinkenberg (1941). The air flow rate is measured by using a mass flow meter whose capacity is 200 ml/min and turndown ratio is 1:100. The air pressure gradient was monitored by using a differential pressure transducer whose accuracy is $\pm 0.25 \text{ \%}$ of 860 kPa of full scale capacity.

During shearing, permeability, and compressional and shear wave velocities were measured simultaneously with the stress-strain and permeability response. The caps confining the both ends of core plug are equipped with piezoelectric transducers to measure the P and S wave velocities of the core sample along core axis. The seismic waves are generated by piezoelectric transducers at one end and registered by a second set of piezoelectric transducers at the other end. The natural frequency of the transducers is 500 kHz. Fig. 1 illustrates the directions of oscillation of transducers. Two different triads of shear wave transducers (indicated as SH and SV) shake the cap in orthogonally different directions. The bedding plane of core sample is aligned parallel to the oscillation direction of SH wave. The other wave (SV) oscillates in the direction perpendicular to the bedding plane. The extent of the intrinsic anisotropy of the shale samples used in the study is quantified based on the degree of shear wave splitting that emerges when a shear wave encounters a discontinuity. Shear waves entering in an anisotropic rock split into two different components oscillating in the respective preferred directions and propagating at different speeds. The degree of intrinsic anisotropy is quantified by means of the shear wave splitting parameter defined as the difference between the split shear wave velocities normalized by

the faster shear wave velocity (Thomsen, 1986). The shear wave splitting parameter is also defined as $(V_{SH} - V_{SV})/V_{SH}$, where V_{SH} and V_{SV} is the shear velocities parallel and perpendicular to the bedding plane, respectively.

Fig. 1. Details of the P and S wave velocity measurements showing relationship between oscillation directions of shear wave velocities relative to bedding plane of shale.

Stress-Dependent Shear and Permeability Behavior of Mancos Shale

Fig. 2a compares the shear stress-strain curve and the change of permeability of shale sample during shearing at $P_c = 2$ MPa. The deviatoric stress is given by $q = \sigma_a - P_c$, where σ_a is axial stress. The sample reaches the yield point at 0.7% of axial strain. In the pre-yield stage, the stress-strain response is almost linear. The permeability gradually decreased from 30 to 12 μD with increasing axial stress in this stage. The decrease of permeability can be attributed to closure of microcracks in the sample. Upon reaching the yield shear stress at around 64 MPa, the sample suddenly lost its stiffness and strain softening ensued. At the same time, the permeability started to abruptly increase from 15 μD . After 1.2% of axial strain, where the permeability reached 380 μD , the permeability hardly changed. The shearing behavior of another core tested at $P_c = 12$ MPa is shown in Fig. 2b. The stress-strain response of this shale shows brittle behavior with a well define peak and strain softening. The yield point occurred at 1.44% of axial strain and 115 MPa of shear stress. The overall trend of permeability change is similar with that observed at $P_c = 2$ MPa. However, the change of permeability became more gradual compared to the previous test. In the pre-yielding stage, the permeability decreased from 83 to 15 μD until the stress reached the yield point. The amount of permeability decrease in pre-yield stage is higher than that at $P_c = 2$ MPa. There is no sign of permeability increase until the sample reached the yield point, whereupon the permeability immediately started to increase. The permeability increased from 15 to 50 μD observed in the very early part of the post-yielding stage and occurred within a small change of axial strain from 1.44 to 2.05%. However, 50 μD of post-yield permeability is still lower than the initial permeability value which is 83 μD . Subsequently, the permeability gradually and continuously increased up to 150 μD until the sample reached 11% of axial strain.

Fig. 2. Changes in stress-strain response and permeability of Mancos shale at confining stress of 2 MPa (left), and 12 MPa (right).

Structural Anisotropy Evolution of Shale During Shear Fracturing

Evaluation of the degree of structural anisotropy of Mancos shale sample was attempted through the shear wave splitting parameter $(V_{SH} - V_{SV})/V_{SH}$. Fig. 3 shows the shear wave splitting parameter changes together with the permeability measurements during shearing of the two tests. For the test at 2 MPa confining stress, the value of splitting parameter slightly increased from 0.048 to 0.062 when the axial stress increased up to the yield stress. But this change of splitting parameter is negligibly small, because the increment of splitting parameter after 0.11% of axial strain is only 0.004. The shear wave splitting parameter tested at $P_c = 12$ MPa intermittently decreased from 0.084 to 0.051 before reaching the yield point. At this period, the permeability decreased consistently. Immediately after reaching the yield point, the splitting parameter value started to increase. The increase of splitting parameter occurred gradually and continuously up to 10% of axial strain. The change of shear wave splitting parameter, which is initially declining and subsequently increasing, correlates well with the permeability change.

Fig. 3. Changes in shear wave splitting parameter and permeability of Mancos shale during shearing at confining stress of 2 MPa (left), and 12 MPa (right).

Relationship Between Fracture Morphology and Hydro-Mechanical Behavior of Shale

After the triaxial tests, the shale core samples were carefully retrieved from the triaxial cell to visually characterize the induced fracture morphologies. Pictures of the samples after shearing with highlighted induced fractures are shown in Fig. 4. Note that the samples were fully intact prior to shearing. For the shale sample tested at $P_c = 2$ MPa, three distinct narrow vertical fractures are observed after shearing. These fractures propagate mainly along the bedding plane of shale sample. For the sample sheared at a confining pressure of $P_c = 12$ MPa, some cracks are observed in the radial direction of core sample after shearing. More significantly, it can be seen that the two conjugated main shear fractures were created. The other fractures running in the radial direction are not considered to develop in an earlier stage of shearing, because these fractures are located on the principal plane of stress on which no shear stress acts.

The observed formation of shear-induced fractures shown in Fig. 4 is consistent with brittle-to-ductile transition behavior of soft rocks showing stress dependency of fracturing behavior as discussed in Nygaard et al. (2006). At low confining stress, brittle vertical fractures were developed along the bedding plane, while conjugated shear fractures formed at high confining stress due to less brittle response. A notable observation is that the vertical fractures, which are typically observed only under tensile stresses or extensional lateral strains, formed for the sample loaded at the confining stress of 2 MPa, which is still a relatively high level of compressive load. These vertical fractures are attributed to local shear stresses generated along the length of the bedding plane due to the undulations. In turn, the local tensile stresses potentially occurred along the bedding planes at each side of plane to ride up the bedding plane undulations. The outcome is the activation and opening up of the bedding planes. The results conclusively show that vertical tensile/extensional can form even in compressional stress regime.

Fig. 4. Mancos shale samples after shearing at confining stresses of 2 MPa (left) and 12 MPa (right). Dotted lines indicate fractures induced after shearing.

From the results presented in Fig. 3 above, it is clear that the evolution of permeability corresponds to the fracturing process. For the test at $P_c = 2$ MPa, the shear wave splitting parameter value hardly changed before yielding. Correspondingly, the permeability decreases but the amount of change is negligibly small. Significant fracturing does not occur in the pre-yielding stage. The sudden increase of permeability observed immediately after yielding can be attributed to development of multiple fractures which suddenly opened along the bedding planes of shale sample within the narrow range of axial strain. At $P_c = 12$ MPa, the gradual and continuous increases of the shear wave splitting parameter and permeability in the post-yield stage suggest that the observed shear fractures were developed gradually with increasing axial strain. The initial decline of permeability observed before yield point is considered to be caused by the closure of microcracks and compression of pore space, because the degree of structural anisotropy evaluated with shear wave splitting parameter simultaneously decreases.

The observed changes of permeability due to closing microcracks and opening fractures during triaxial test can be organized in a simple relationship between the permeability and shear wave splitting parameter as shown in Fig. 5. In the pre-yield stages, the permeability decreases with decreasing shear wave splitting parameter. Fracture evolution after yielding increases both the permeability and shear wave splitting parameter. Interestingly, the two test results obtained at the different confining stress conditions are consistent in this relationship. The shear wave splitting parameter appears to be a good index parameter that can be used as indicator of permeability changes in shale subjected to shearing.

Fig. 5. Relationship between permeability and shear wave splitting parameter.

Conclusions

Triaxial compression tests were carried out on dry core plugs of organic-rich Mancos shale at 2 and 12 MPa of confining stresses to relate the change of hydro-mechanical and seismic properties of shale with development of structural anisotropy due to shear fracture development. The air permeability and P and S wave velocities of shale samples were measured simultaneously with the stress-strain response during the triaxial tests. The following are the main conclusions from the study: 1) Permeability parallel to bedding plane decreases pre-peak (due to compaction), but increases significantly post-peak due to fracturing; 2) The shear

wave splitting parameter decreases and increases correspondingly with permeability in the pre- and post-failure stages; 3) Induced fracture morphology changes from tensile to shearing fractures with increasing confining pressure; 4) Initial heterogeneity appears to enhance the brittleness of shale, and to affect the failure mode (i.e., tensile fracturing along the bedding plane at low confinement, and branching of shear fractures along bedding planes at high confinement); 5) Tensile fracturing can occur in a compressional regime in shales during shearing along pre-existing undulating bedding plane joints; and 6) The shear wave splitting parameter can be a useful index for monitoring permeability changes and fracturing of shales during to shearing.

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